

Paper 1

**SCHOLARLY PUBLICATION BASED RESEARCH
JOURNALS CLASSIFICATION – NEW INSIGHT-
BASED MODEL**

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Abstract

Research is an essential activity in Society for technology, industrial, and social progress. Based on the historical review, higher education institutions focus on basic, conceptual, explorative, empirical, and analytical research methods whereas industries focus on new products and new processes development. In this paper, based on a survey on closed and open access scholarly publications, a new Scholarly Publication based Research Journals Classification model is proposed by defining an ideal scholarly publication process, analysing scholarly publication process, determining necessary and sufficient conditions to call an article as Scholarly article, identifying and analysing various factors affecting Journal classification, and developing a new model of Scholarly Journals grading.

Keywords : Scholarly publication, Scholarly journals, ABCD journal ranking, Journal classification, Ideal model of scholarly publication.

1. INTRODUCTION :

Research is an important activity in higher education institutions, research institutions, and industries. Research and Development is an essential activity for technology, industrial, and social progress. Based on the historical review, higher education institutions focus on basic, conceptual, explorative, empirical, and analytical research methods whereas industries focus on new products and new processes development. It is also known that the end of every piece of research of HEIs and Research Institutions is the scholarly publication and having the copyright of such basic or conceptual invention whereas the end of every piece of research of industries is acquiring a patent in inventor/company name. As mentioned in previous publications, scholarly research is basically involved in generating *new knowledge* through a systematic method or it is a method of a *new interpretation* of existing knowledge about any system by means of analysing it using suitable framework [1], [2], [3], [4].

As per one school of thought, there are two universally practiced and easily comprehensible types of research. They are exploratory research and descriptive research. Explorative research is based upon the objectives of solving the problem of study to make a decision related to it and is usually unstructured and qualitative in nature. The descriptive study is involved in describing a system mainly in terms of its functions and characteristics, and environment and end up to a conclusion about the system based on the purposes of the study and is usually structured and quantitative in nature.

2. RELATED WORKS :

There are many research work and scholarly publications in the area of Scholarly publication, Journal quality, Journal citation based impact factors, and Journal indexing. Table 1 depicts some of such scholarly papers in the field with the corresponding reference.

Table 1 : Some of the related scholarly work and publications during last few years.

S. No.	Issues	Focus	Reference
5	Problems in Conventional Scholarly Publications	Publishing delay	Björk, B. C., et al. (2013). [5]
6	Problems in Conventional Scholarly Publications	Publisher monopoly power and third-degree price discrimination	Chressanthis, G. A., (1993). [6]
7	Open Access Scholarly Publication	To provide open educational resource everybody with no cost	Anderson, T. (2013). [7]
8	Open Access Scholarly Publication	As a new scholarly communication model	Yiotis, K. (2005). [8]
9	Open Access Scholarly Publication	Challenges of open access publication	Ramalho Correia, A. M., et al. (2005). [9]
10	Open Access Scholarly Publication	Use of electronic media for open access publication to the globe	Oppenheim, C. (2008). [10]
11	Open Access Scholarly Publication	How internet changed the scholarly publications	Bartling, S. et al. (2014). [11]
12	Open Access Scholarly Publication	study of conflicting paradigms of Institutional repositories, open access, and scholarly Publication	Cullen, R. et al. (2011). [12]
13	Open Access Scholarly Publication	Study of innovative features	Björk, B. C. (2011). [13]
14	Open Access Scholarly Publication	Characteristics based on multidisciplinary study	Kousha, K. (2009). [14]
15	Predatory publishers	Predatory open-access scholarly publishers	Beall, J. (2010). [15]
16	Predatory publishers	Predatory publishers are corrupting open access	Beall, J. (2012). [16]
17	Predatory publishers	Unethical practices in scholarly, open-access publishing	Beall, J. (2013). [17]
18	Predatory publishers	Criteria for determining predatory open-access publishers	Beall, J. (2015). [18]
19	Predatory publishers	Essential information about predatory publishers and journals	Beall, J. (2016). [19]
20	Predatory publishers	What value do journal whitelists and blacklists have in academia?	da Silva, J. A. T., et al. (2018). [20]
21	Predatory publishers	Predatory journals in library	Nelson, N., et al.

		databases: How much should we worry?	(2015). [21]
22	Innovations in Scholarly Publication	Rethinking scholarly communication: building the system that scholars deserve] Sompel, H. V. D., et al. (2004). [22]
23	Innovations in Scholarly Publication	Why Smart Researcher Hesitate to Publish in/with Top Ranking Journals/Publishers	Aithal, P. S., et al. (2016). [23]
24	Innovations in Scholarly Publication	Comparative Study of Various Research Indices used to measure quality of Research Publications	Aithal, P. S., et al. (2016). [24]
25	Innovations in Scholarly Publication	A study comparing commercial and nonprofit/university publishers	Moghaddam, G. G. (2007). [25]
26	Innovations in Scholarly Publication	Wikipedia and academic peer review: Wikipedia as a recognised medium for scholarly publication	Black, E. W. (2008). [26]
27	Innovations in Scholarly Publication	Opening up institutional repositories: social construction of innovation in scholarly communication	Rieger, O. Y. (2008). [27]
28	Journal Rating & Ranking	How robust is journal rating in Humanities and Social Sciences	Ferrara, A., (2016). [28]
29	Journal Rating & Ranking	Towards a consolidation of worldwide journal rankings—a classification using random forests and aggregate rating	Tüselmann, H., et al. (2015). [29]
30	Journal Rating & Ranking	A Google Scholar h-index for journals: An alternative metric to measure journal impact in economics and business	Harzing, A. W., (2009). [30]
31	Journal Rating & Ranking	The journal impact factor: a brief history, critique, and discussion of adverse effects	Larivière, V., et al. (2018). [31]
32	Journal Rating & Ranking	On the stability of citation-based journal rankings	Pajić, D. (2015). [32]
33	Journal Rating & Ranking	Ranking the management journals	Harris, C. (2008). [33]
34	Journal Rating & Ranking	Ranking journals using altmetrics	Loach, T. V., et al. (2015). [34]
35	Journal Rating & Ranking	Journal ranking by citation analysis: Some inconsistencies	Over, R. (1978). [35]

3. OBJECTIVES :

- (1) To define ideal scholarly publication process
- (2) To analyse Scholarly publication process
- (3) To determine necessary and sufficient conditions to call an article as Scholarly article
- (4) To identify and analyse various factors affecting Journal classification
- (5) To develop a new model of Scholarly Journals grading

4. METHODOLOGY :

Conceptual study on ideal system model [36] based on explorative research using trend analysis. The methodology uses the definition of ideal system in a given topic in terms of its properties and studies present status or trend of the same system and analyse how the present system can be improved towards ideal system with ideal characteristics.

5. IDEAL RESEARCH MODEL :

As per the concept of ideal research, it is a process of creating new knowledge open to society without any intension of retaining its control in the form of copyright or patent. Any invention or finding should end with open access publication to the entire world to share the generated new knowledge to the society for solving existing problems or for further research by interested researchers or research groups.

According to present model, any research can be broadly classified into two types as Scientific research and Industrial research. Scientific research is also called pure research and industrial research is also called applied research. All research related to new concept based knowledge creation is considered under scientific or pure research and all research related new product or new process based knowledge creation is considered as industrial research or applied research as summarized in table 2.

Table 2 : Type of scholarly research and the nature IPR generated

S.No.	Classification of Research	Input	Output	IPR Generated
1	Scientific or Pure Research (Academic research)	Intangible/Tangible resources	Theory/Concept/Models	Copyright
2	Industrial or Applied Research	Tangible Resources	Product/Process/Service	Patent

6. SCHOLARLY PUBLICATION PROCESS :

6.1 Scholarly Article Format :

The outcome of research presented systematically in the form of a structured document is generally called as scholarly research paper or scholarly article. The format of a scholarly article in general consists of following parts in its structure :

- (1) Introduction
- (2) Review of Literature / Related work
- (3) Objectives of research
- (4) Experimental Details / Methodology
- (5) Result & Discussion / Analysis & Interpretation
- (6) Findings/Suggestions/Recommendations

(7) Conclusion

(8) References of citations in MLA/ APA/ Chicago/ Harvard/ Vancouver style

The structural difference between a scientific and social science scholarly article is depicted in table 3.

Table 3 : Structural Difference between the Scientific Scholarly article framework and Social science & management Scholarly article framework

S. No.	Scientific Scholarly article framework	Social science & management Scholarly article framework
1	Abstract	Abstract
2	Introduction	Introduction
3	Review of Literature	Related work
4	Objectives	Objectives
5	Experimental Details	Methodology
6	Result & Discussion	Analysis & Interpretation
7	Findings	Suggestion/Recommendation
8	Conclusion	Conclusion
9	References of citations in APA/ Vancouver style	References of citations in MLA/ APA/ Chicago/ Harvard style
10	Formatted document	Formatted document

The objective of every author while writing a Scholarly Article is to publish it freely to the entire world immediately at no cost. Before the advent of the internet and online open publication model, authors used to find suitable publishers who publish scholarly articles in a similar subject in the form of a book called scholarly journal. The scholarly journal publishers are mediators to check the article quality (language in terms of grammar, novelty, plagiarism, and format) of such an article by means of a checking process called review of scholarly article. After the advent of the internet and various application software, checking the grammar mistakes (language quality), detecting plagiarism (originality), and systematic formatting as scholarly article became easy and the author of the article can take care of these things independently using a well supportive computer system. The peer review process became important only to know the novelty in the form of new knowledge, or a new interpretation of it. In olden days, since, all researchers had no access to computers, publishers took responsibility of language improvement including grammar, checking the plagiarism to confirm the originality of the paper as scholarly article and to check the novelty to publish and supply it to all research & higher education libraries across the globe. In return, they bargained heavily to capture the copyright of the scholarly article for a lifetime. The poor researchers had no alternative to showcase their research findings to the entire world so that they have accepted the proposal of scholarly publication. The publishers not only became successful in grabbing the copyright of the research papers developed by the poor researchers but also tried to create a monopoly by creating the process called blind peer review process. The blind peer review process is publisher focussed and has an objective of adding business value (selling value) of the paper along with improving the grammar, checking the plagiarism, and formatting the paper as per journal publication format to make the printed version of scholarly journal attractive which intern enhanced the Journal subscription across the globe. Usually, the peer review is done by three people, one is internal from the publishing house and the other two are outsiders usually chosen from the author

suggestive list. The internal reviewer checks the subject for suitability of the paper for including in a requested journal, check grammar and language for any corrections, check the plagiarism, and format it. Then the paper is reviewed by two reviewers positively related to that subject to ensure novelty in the form of new knowledge, or new analysis-based interpretation. Since the journal publishers are not paying for the external review process, the external reviewer usually does not give priority and hence review process takes a long time. The publisher takes the decision to accept the paper if they feel that the paper is sellable for a long time and ask the author to transfer the copyright of the paper in publisher name and enjoys the revenue of selling that paper throughout the globe forever. The poor author will get satisfaction by seeing the published paper and the copies of the printed papers he received. Once the copyright is transferred, the author cannot share the paper officially in any form. Hence scholarly publication became big business and many journals started to charge the author in the name of journal submission charges along with earnings by selling the copyright received articles. Thus, the scholarly publication model became an attractive business model with high profit, which further increased competition. Many publishers encashed this opportunity and grown as multinational publishers with several millions of annual revenues. Table 4 lists some of the prominent multinational publishers with an approximate number of journals they publish in different subjects. These publishers called big-players in the journal and books publication field started to control their monopoly by means of a strategy to block new entrants in scholarly publications. The two strategies the big-player used to protect themselves are (1) Scopus & Web of Science Indexing, (2) Creation of a new field of publishers called predatory publishers. The big players in scholarly publications have started their own Journal indexing database and blocked the new players entry to their journal indexing database. They created a lobby that started to call new entrants to scholarly Journal Publication business as “predatory journals”. It is assumed that many researchers are sponsored for such hue and cry against small journal publishers and new publishers and they started to write articles continuously for every two years to keep the predatory publication issue alive. For example, it is difficult to find out why Mr. Beall, J. [15-19] continuously wrote against predatory journals and has gone to such extent to list such journals without much supporting documentary evidence.

Table 4 : List of Top multinational publishers with number of Journals and annual revenue

S. No.	Top multinational publishers	Number of Journals [23]	Annual Revenue
1	Elsevier Journals	3,352	£2.54 billion (2018)
2	Springer-Verlag	2,700	Euro1.64 billion (2017)
3	John Wiley and Sons	2,380	\$1.80 billion (2019)
4	Taylor and Francis	2,100	£530 millions (2017)
5	Sage Publications	1,300	£2.54 billion (2018)
6	Walter de Gruyter	913	\$15 million (2018)
7	Inderscience Publishers	391	-
9	Hindawi Publishing Corporation	366	-
10	Cambridge University Press	329	£327 million (2019)
11	Oxford University Press	310	£840 million (2018)
12	Emerald	308	£380 million (20 8)

6.2 Re-defining Predatory Journals :

As per our model, scholarly publication is the contribution from researchers for society and for the continuation of research further by many other related research groups for the development of science and society. Hence scholarly publication should not be a business proposition and only charitable organizations should involve in publication of research output. It can be argued that the organizations who involve in scholarly journal business are looking for profit and hence they cannot give justice for scholarly publication. Their strategy would be to create a business model which subsequently make them monopoly to get highest revenue and huge profit by exploiting both scholarly authors and other researchers who wants to read and continue such work as further research. A real and genuine scholarly journal will not profit motivated and start publishing service under charity model to help the researchers and the society to spread the research results for promoting research and extension to society. Using internet based online publication model, the charitable organizations which involve in scholarly publication can decrease their cost to minimum so that they can sustain for longer time using charity based free publication and free distribution model. Such journals published by charity motivated publishers with no cost to authors and readers is called non-predatory journals. Table 5 compares non-predatory and predatory journals.

Table 5 : Comparison of non-predatory and predatory journals based on 5 factors

S. No.	Factors	Non-predatory Journal	Predatory Journal
1	Submission charge	Free	Paid
2	Processing Charge	Free	Paid
3	Copyright	With authors	With Publishers
4	Subscription charge	Free open access	Paid subscription
5	Time delay	Minimum	Long waiting
6	Availability	Online open access copy	Printed copy
7	Review (Free/Paid)	No payment to reviewer	No payment to reviewer
8	Profit	Not profit motivated	Profit motivated

Based on table 5, the new definition of predatory journal is a journal published by profit motivated publishers and they charge either to author or to reader or both. The authors should voluntarily ban such predatory publishers to retail the copyright of their scholarly paper and to publish it globally without much time lag and for free distribution.

7. SCHOLARLY JOURNALS :

As mentioned in the previous section, the objective of scholarly publication is the distribution of the research results systematically in the form of a scholarly article to every person who has the interest to read or use it as reference information in their research without constraints which keep him to avoid such publication. Thus, scholarly journals should have the intention to fulfil the objective of scholarly publication. As per table 7, scholarly journals should have the following objects from authors and readers point of view :

- (1) Low time lag between submission & publication by accelerating review process.
- (2) Moderate review to check the novelty, plagiarism, language, and format of the research publication.
- (3) Zero submission and processing charge for the authors since research is a social contribution effort.

- (4) Open online publication with no article download cost for readers.
- (5) The copyright should be with the author so that he can use and distribute the paper in other means like sharing through various social media in addition to the journal website.
- (6) A unique identification number has to be given to the article for easy search and downloading purpose.
- (7) The published paper should be available for download forever for DOI based searching by storing it in multiple locations.

7.1 Types of Scholarly Journals :

As per the present model, scholarly journals can be classified as :

- (1) Non-profit & charitable organization supported Journals
- (2) Non-profit motivated independent Journals,
- (3) Profit motivated organizations Journal as a business product
- (4) Profit motivated individuals published Journals as their business products
- (5) Self publication by authors using social networks or open online libraries

The above publishers follow either open access or closed access scholarly publication model [37]. Open access model (new model) may follow either free publication without Article processing charge (APC) or collect APC from the authors which usually vary from \$ 20 to \$ 5,000. In an open access publication model, some journals insist APC and compulsory copyright to publisher name but many other journals allow authors to retain copyright in the author's name. In the closed access model (old model) the publisher is controlling the system by following the subscription model of journal distribution. For this, the publisher insists the author to transfer the copyright of the article and earns huge money by selling the paper & journal thereafter. In this model, some publishers even charge article submission charges and APC from authors along with copy transfer to sell the article through subscription and online downloads. The closed publication model is a rude (one sided) model where both the author and the reviewer will not get any financial benefit for their efforts.

7.2 Necessary & Sufficient conditions to call an article as Scholarly article :

In this section, an attempt is made to systematically explain scholarly article by postulating its properties under necessary and sufficient conditions.

Necessary Conditions for Scholarly Article :

- (1) Novelty /New knowledge or new interpretation of existing knowledge.
- (2) Plagiarism free.
- (3) Related works.
- (4) Systematic Study : to prove that the research is systematic.
- (5) An abstract of the research work.

Sufficient Conditions for Scholarly Article :

- (1) Systematic scholarly Format : language.
- (2) Objectives of study.
- (3) Citations in the article.
- (4) Conclusion about the findings.
- (5) Scholarly references.

A journal which publishes non-scholarly articles is called Magazine or Predatory Journal.

7.3 Factors affecting Journal classification :

Factors Affecting Journal Classification are :

- (1) New Knowledge, based on New Analysis/ New experiment,
- (2) Open & free Access to entire globe
- (3) Free Publication for authors
- (4) Copy right is with Authors

7.4 New model of Scholarly Journals grading :

Presently there are different models and methods of ranking the journals which include, based on citations, based on indexing, based on altmetrics, etc. Table 6 list the features compared in such ranking.

Table 6 : Features used in Journal ranking

S. No.	Journal Ranking Model	Features used / compared
1	Citation Based Approach	Citation based impact factor [38]
2	Altmetrics based Approach	Social Media Approach [39]
3	Impact factor of the Journal	Impact factors of Journals [40]
4	H-Index of the Journal	H-index values of Journals [24, 41]

7.5 Scholarly Journal Categories :

As per our observations, a scholarly journal falls into one of the following categories :

- (1) Closed access based Paid subscription, with author processing charge (APC) and Copyright transferred from the author.
- (2) Closed access based paid subscription, without author processing charge (APC) and Copyright transferred from the author.
- (3) Open Access Free Publication by taking APC and Copyright from the author.
- (4) Open Access Free Publication without taking APC and Copyright from the author.

Accordingly, they can be divided into different grades as shown below :

- (1) **A Grade** – University/HEI owned Open access, Free Publication Journals without taking Copyright.
- (2) **B Grade** – University/HEI owned Open access Journals with copyright or APC.
- (3) **C Grade** – Commercial Organizational Publishers Journals with Closed access with copyright or APC.
- (4) **D Grade** – Individually/commercial organization owned Journals with Closed access, APC & copyright.

This new Journal grading model from authors and readers point of view is further explained using table 7.

Table 7 : ABCD Model of Researcher Centric Scholarly Journals Grading

S. No.	Grade	Open Access	No Article Processing Charges	Copyright with Authors	Example
1	A	Yes	Yes	Yes	Open access Journals published by the charitable organization, sponsored by Universities, etc.

					without any APC and copyright transfer. (Diamond OA Journals)
2	B++	Yes	Yes	No	Open access but follows subscription model also to take care of expenses by collecting copyright. (Gold OA journals)
3	B+	Yes	No	Yes	Open access but collects a small amount of APC from authors or their sponsoring organization. (Silver OA Journals)
4	B	Yes	No	No	Open access but collects a small amount of APC from authors or their sponsoring organization and also follows subscription model to libraries.
5	C++	No	Yes	Yes	Closed access but no APC and copyright transfer, but sells paper through a library subscription.
6	C+	No	Yes	No	Closed access and copyright transfer, but no APC but sells paper through subscription and article download charges.
7	C	No	No	Yes	Closed access and no copyright transfer, but collects APC and sells paper through a library subscription.
8	D	No	No	No	Closed access, copyright transfer, collects APC and sells paper through library subscription and article download charges.

8. CONCLUSION :

The objective of research and development is simplifying complex things to generate new knowledge or new interpretation. The continuous progress in technology is supporting the researchers to improve the quality and decreasing the time duration required for each research process. Scholarly publication is a part of every research and has the objective of spreading the research results to other researchers in the same field to boost the further research by many groups with an intention to accelerate the continued growth of the subject in society. Currently, many publishers involved in scholarly publications treated it as a profitable business model and all processes under scholarly publications are publisher centric. Hence, they controlled the scholarly publication model from their survival point of view by creating many lobby-based survival strategies including Journal indexing. In the process, they imposed article submission charges, article processing charges, copyright transfer to their name to sell the articles and journals to the public. Since this publication model is publisher centric and in the name of peer review, they have hijacked the entire research effort of the

researcher to their control and hesitated to share the revenue with the authors. The researchers were handicapped to raise their voices against this system due to the continued lobby of international publishers to the scholarly publication process. As we know, changes are inevitable in any and every system, the advent of technology gave a solution to researchers to come out of the monopoly of publishers' model. Now, through online open access and holding copyright with the researcher, scholarly publication is expected to be researcher centric. Many philanthropic and charitable organizations started to support this researcher centric model to give justice to researchers and fulfil the real objective of scholarly publication. In this proposed researcher centric scholarly article publication model, three parameters are considered to classify research journals which include, (1) Open access publication, (2) Article Processing Charge (APC), and (3) Retaining copyright with the authors. Based on these three parameters eight grades of research journals are identified and named them as A grade, B++ grade, B+ grade, B grade, C++ grade, C+ grade, C grade, and D grade as listed in table 7. The developed model of journal classification is compared with existing Journal grading models and some suggestions made on scholarly publications and citations from different stakeholders' points of view. Based on our arguments, it is observed that the online electronic journals published by universities, libraries, organizations with research publication grants, and the scholarly societies in each specialty areas are optimum journals to support researchers honestly by falling the category of A grade Journals to uphold the objective, freedom, integrity, and self-respect of the researchers in their endeavour of serving the society. This Researcher centric Scholarly Journals grading and publication model is expected to surpass the prevailing Publisher centric model in future days.

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